

Addressing Internet Dependency in Low-Resource Cambodian Commune Offices: Design and Development of a Lightweight Offline-First Document Management System

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Abstract-In Cambodia, commune offices manage critical civil documents such as birth, marriage, death certificates but a large majority of commune offices use paper-based systems, which are slow, hard to handle, and at risk of losing essential documents. For many, cloud-based solutions are unlikely to be feasible due to unreliable internet connections and limited hardware resources. This research outlines an offline-first document management system for the administration at commune level that was designed, developed, and evaluated. This document management system was created using Laravel, MySQL, Bootstrap 5 and Progressive Web Application (PWA) technologies. A survey of 156 citizens and interviews with the staff of five commune offices throughout Phnom Penh provided the basis for determining requirements. Using the Design Science Research methodology enabled the evaluation of the document management system within a simulated commune office environment. Document retrieval times were demonstrated to have diminished from approximately 24 minutes to 2.5 seconds. All users met 100% compliance with role-based access control, there was a successful offline synchronization with a rate of 95% and users were very satisfied with the document management system receiving an average score of 4.8 on a scale of 5. This study demonstrates that offline-first Progressive Web Applications can be an effective means of increasing the efficiency of document management in government offices with limited resources.

Index Terms - Offline-first, Progressive Web Application, document management system, e-government, civil registration, role-based access control, Design Science Research, low-resource environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main function of local government is the management of Administrative documents. The commune offices of Cambodia are the main interface for citizens to access services from the government and to receive copies of civil records such as birth, marriage and death

certificates, which are used as proof of their identity, family circumstances and civil registration. These records form the local element of the civil registration and vital statistics system in Cambodia, which is viewed by the global development community as the basis for legal identity, public planning legal identity for all [2]. The commune offices are still primarily paper based since the early 2000s [1]; creating a timely opportunity for digital transformation.

Finding records on paper is challenging due to their fragility, which undermines delivery of service and internal administration [3]. Staff and citizens both experience the impacts of this situation: In our needs assessment conducted for this study, we found that commune staff were generally able to retrieve a record from a file within an average of about 24 minutes and that 83.3% of the citizens we surveyed had come back to the same commune office for the same document more than once. There is extensive documentation addressing difficulties with using paper-based systems in the public sector, and government entities in developing nations are increasingly coming to understand the importance of utilizing digital technology in order to better manage their content and processes [4], [18].

The Royal Government of Cambodia has recognized this necessity in the 'Cambodia Digital Government Policy 2022-2035', which designates electronic document management as a high-priority activity within the country [5]. Electronic Document Management Systems have been shown to improve the efficiency of processing and improve the reliability of the documents produced [6]. In addition, there is evidence that the implementation of electronic records systems in an office setting has a positive effect on employee productivity [7]. However, the implementation of EDMS processes at the commune level has been limited to date because many of the current EDMS solutions require continuous network connectivity, which commune offices often cannot provide due to the unstable internet connection and use of equipment with limited specifications [9].

This study was designed, developed, and evaluated to create a lightweight document management system for Cambodian commune offices using an offline-first design principle [10][12] and Progressive Web Applications

(PWA) [11], enabling the document management system to work with basic hardware and a Local Area Network (LAN) without any or limited connectivity. The document management system's main contributions include: (i) An empirical needs assessment of document management practice at the commune level using a citizen survey and staff interviews at five commune offices; (ii) A working prototype of an offline-first document management system at the commune level; (iii) A working implementation of the document management system using Laravel, MySQL, Bootstrap 5, PWA offline components, and a multilayered security model; and (iv) An evaluation of how efficiently, securely, and reliably the last-mile delivery of documents occurred, as well as an evaluation of how acceptable the document management system was to users, given that each of these evaluations were simulated conditions reflective of Cambodian commune offices.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Document Management and Electronic Records in the Public Sector

For Effective document management, decision-making assistance, and efficiency in delivering services, effective document management is vital to public sector organizations [6]. Research repeatedly states the disadvantages associated with paper-based document management systems, such as slow retrieval times, high potential for physical damage/loss, limited storage capacities and ease of unauthorized access [3]. As a result, conversion from paper-based document management systems to EDMS has been seen as an effective strategy as it will lead to providing a structured and organized digital environment for storing, indexing, searching for and retrieving electronic records [6]. Transitioning to EDMS solutions is not always a simple task, according to evidence from EDMS deployments conducted in developing countries, which show that there have often been issues with the transition to electronic records management due to institutional and infrastructural constraints in sub-Saharan Africa, such as lack of skilled personnel or unreliable infrastructure; the case studies of adopting EDMS solutions within government agencies in the UK, the Botswana Ministry of Trade and Industry and Sarawak Malaysia's State Government all demonstrate similar patterns: that technology alone will not guarantee success; ownership by users, effective training and successful alignment with existing workflows are crucial to achieving a successful outcome. These findings contributed to the design of the requirements-elicitation and user-acceptance evaluation in this study.

B. E-Government in Developing Countries and in Cambodia

Limited ICT infrastructure and digital capacity frequently impede the adoption of e-Government by developing countries [4], and the reasons for why they lag behind the ambition of their policies in the adoption of these technologies has generated considerable literature

[19]. One of the most cited explanations of why there is such a high failure rate of e-government projects in developing and transitional countries is Heeks's design-reality gap model [8]. Cambodia is an example of a country facing these types of challenges. Early work identified the problems of infrastructure, management and human capacity facing e-Government in Cambodia [9]; more recent analyses continue to find that rural connectivity and low levels of digital literacy still remain the major barriers to the country's digital government agenda, despite clear national policy commitments [5]. Because of these findings, studies examining digital systems in similar circumstances suggest that simplicity, minimum resource requirements, and ease of use should be the priority for maximizing the likelihood of adoption for these types of systems [4]. The system which is presented in this paper has been designed specifically to meet these design criteria.

C. Offline-First Design and Progressive Web Applications

An offline-first design considers network connectivity an optional enhancement rather than a core requirement. Data will be stored and processed locally and synchronized to the cloud once a connection becomes available [10]. Kleppmann et al. describe a similar idea called 'local-first', where the main copy of the data resides on the local device and is synchronized as soon as an opportunistic connection becomes possible, such as via local WiFi; they assert that this enhances the availability, responsiveness and user control of the information [12]. PWAs embody these concepts in the browser using Service Workers, IndexedDB and the Background Synchronization API; they are also considered to be a cost-effective and technically viable option for areas that lack reliable internet connectivity [10], [11]. Empirical studies on the operational characteristics of these three technologies also indicate that they are suitable to low-resourced environments because they demonstrate sufficient levels of both energy and resource efficiency through the use of Service Worker caching [20] and due to their ability to measurably enhance PWA performance when properly configured [21]. However, researchers and security analysts have warned that if PWAs are not carefully set up, their capabilities have the potential to be abused [22], which is an especially relevant point when the managed content consists of sensitive record types, such as civil records. The present study transfers this established pattern from the health domain to commune-level civil-records administration.

D. Role-Based Access Control

Access control is considered a critical aspect of civil record data, which are classified as sensitive. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is used for assigning permissions to roles rather than individuals so that each user is limited to only the functions that they require based on their responsibilities. This model of RBAC was first proposed by Ferraiolo and Kuhn [23], and then later formalized as part of the RBAC96 family of models by Sandhu et al. [24]. RBAC is therefore particularly well-suited to the organization of small government offices such as commune

offices throughout Cambodia where the division of responsibilities is stable and divided into simple, auditable roles such as administration/clerk/staff. The role structure makes RBAC easy to use, administer and securely monitor without requiring any specialized staff to monitor or administer security.

E. Research Gap

Prior research has studied EDMS, e-government, PWAs and RBAC individually but has not examined their integration into an offline-first document management system with empirical evaluation for the unique operational challenges faced by commune offices in developing countries. Specific to the EDMS literature reviewed previously, most studies have assumed a level of reliable connectivity or have focused on organizational barriers rather than the infrastructure barriers; whereas, the offline-first and PWA literature fail to address the issue of managing government records. The purpose of this study is to fill the gap as outlined above.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

For this research, Design Science Research (DSR) is used as a methodological approach to solving real-world problems through the creation and evaluation of innovative artifacts, and DSR is an appropriate methodological choice as the purpose of this research is to design and evaluate a software artifact for a real-world problem, and not simply describe it. The DSR process represented in this research followed the six activities described by the DSR model [13]: (1) problem identification; (2) definition of objectives; (3) design and development; (4) demonstration; (5) evaluation; and (6) communication. The evaluation strategy used for this research conforms to the artificial evaluation, whereby the evaluation took place in a controlled, simulated environment, one formed during the DSR development and utilized together as a summative evaluation against performance goals and as part of future research in a naturalistic setting.

B. Requirements Elicitation and Needs Assessment

The requirements were created based on the preliminary data collection, which included a survey of 156 citizens and structured interviews with staff from five commune offices in Phnom Penh. The citizen survey was conducted in two ways to include respondents with limited digital skills: through an online Google Forms platform and with an identical paper copy. The survey asked citizens questions on how often they visited the commune office, what types of documents were requested, how long they waited for documents, how many times they visited for the same document, their level of satisfaction with the current paper-based service, and their willingness to use and recommend legally valid digital documents. Both formats used a combination of categorical items and five-point Likert-scale statements. The staff interviews used a structured questionnaire that asked staff to report on the

record types they handle, how they currently store and retrieve those records, how long it takes them to manually search for a record, what the connectivity and hardware conditions are in their office, and what type of system they would like to see implemented. Participation in both data collection instruments was voluntary, and the purpose of the study was explained to participants prior to their participation. The needs assessment confirmed that birth, marriage, and death certificates are the main record types, that manual retrieval is the primary bottleneck, and that offline-first operation is a key requirement; a quantitative summary of the findings are provided in Section IV-A.

C. System Architecture

A LAN-based architecture implements the networked system while a stand-alone communal networked server computer resides on the LAN, which contains the Laravel application and MySQL database, and end users connect to the server via the server's IP address through a web browser without any client machine software required to access the system. In addition, there is an offline-first PWA layer between the client (end users) and the server: a Service Worker to intercept requests made to the server; cached pages may be served while offline; an IndexedDB to queue citizen records and document uploads made when there is no network access; and a Background Synchronization API to automatically send queued records to the server once there is connectivity. Because all data is stored locally in an office, the system works as if no network is required to support day-to-day business operations, allowing for uninterrupted operation from upstream network outages.

D. Implementation

Technologies that meet the operational constraints of commune offices were chosen as shown in table/figure I. Laravel was selected due to its functionality for role management, authentication and file management and lower resource usage than competing tools [14]. MySQL provides secure, low-resource persistent storage with the ability to backup and restore using simple methods, can easily be integrated into Laravel via Eloquent ORM [15], and can be optimised to run on limited hardware. Bootstrap 5 will provide fast page loading times and cross browser support even on low-specification hardware [16]. The components from the PWA will enable the offline-first behaviour described previously [11].

Table I
SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION TECHNOLOGIES

Layer	Technology	Role in the system
Backend	Laravel (PHP)	Authentication, RBAC, file handling, business logic
Database	MySQL	Local storage of citizen records and document metadata
Front end	Bootstrap 5	Lightweight, responsive, fast-loading interface

Offline	Service Worker	Caches pages for offline navigation
Offline	IndexedDB	Queues records and uploads created while offline
Offline	Background Sync API	Auto-synchronizes queued data on reconnection

After conducting staff interviews, it was determined that eight core functions have been included in the system: citizen record management, document upload and categorization by type, searching and filtering for documents by name, national ID, or category, role-based access control for administrator, clerk and staff access levels, ability to queue documents for upload while offline using a web service, backup capability providing downloadable archives of previously uploaded documents, a statistics dashboard, and user management limited to administrators. In addition to the RBAC mechanism, a multi-layered security model was utilized based on the level of sensitivity of civil records and includes: storing passwords using salted hashes; encrypting uploaded document files when they are stored; capturing security-related actions in an audit log; and terminating sessions after a period of inactivity.

E. Evaluation Procedure and Metrics

The artifact was demonstrated and evaluated in a simulated commune environment built to reflect real conditions observed during data collection: four laptops with basic specifications connected through a local WiFi network, with the client periodically disconnected to emulate network failure. The hardware specifications are given in Table II. Descriptive statistics were used throughout [17]. Frequency and percentage distribution were computed as

$$\text{Percentage} = (f / N) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency of an outcome and N is the total number of cases. Mean document retrieval time was computed as

$$\bar{x} = (\Sigma x) / n \quad (2)$$

where Σx is the total recorded time and n is the number of observations. The efficiency gain over the paper-based process was measured as percentage improvement,

$$\text{Improvement} = ((\text{Old} - \text{New}) / \text{Old}) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where Old and New are the average retrieval times of the paper-based and proposed systems, respectively. Four evaluation strands were conducted: (i) a retrieval-time comparison against the staff-reported manual search times gathered in the needs assessment; (ii) 30 RBAC test cases across the three roles; (iii) 40 offline test cycles in which data entered while disconnected was checked for correct local storage and successful synchronization on reconnection, against a predefined 90% success target; and (iv) User Acceptance Testing (UAT), in which clerks from the five participating commune offices used the system and

rated ten statements covering the eight core features and overall satisfaction on a five-point Likert scale. Page load time on the test hardware was also recorded.

F. Inferential Statistical Tests

To verify the hypotheses, inferential statistics were also performed on the quantitative data in addition to the descriptive statistics described above. Given the small sample sizes and lack of normality, non-parametric tests were used as appropriate. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test compared the average document retrieval times from both the paper-based system and the proposed system to determine if there was a statistically significant time savings in retrieval time (SOP 1). A one-sample t-test was applied to evaluate weighted mean UAT scores against the midpoint of a neutral scale (3.0) to assess whether staff were significantly above neutral in acceptance of system functionality (SOP 2). An exact binomial test was conducted to assess if the compliance rate for role-based access control and offline synchronization success rate are statistically above a benchmark of 90% (SOP 1 and SOP 3). The alpha level for all tests was set to 0.05, and each test was conducted as one-tailed, as specified in the respective directional hypotheses.

Table II
HARDWARE SPECIFICATIONS OF THE TESTING ENVIRONMENT

Component	Specification
Server processor	Intel Core i5-4590
Server memory (RAM)	8 GB
Client processor	Intel Core i3-4130
Client memory (RAM)	4 GB
Operating system	Windows 10
Network type	Local WiFi connection

IV. RESULTS

A. Needs Assessment Findings

Staff interviews were utilized in order to establish a baseline level of activity for the paper-based process. The documented duration for a manual searching through records varied by office, as evidenced by Table III, with search times from more than 10 minutes to over 40 minutes per record - averaging 24 minutes for the five offices combined. Staff indicated that these variations were due to a lack of proper record management and filing discipline; the volume of records held at the time of the request; and the age of the individual record requested.

Table III
REPORTED MANUAL SEARCH TIME BY COMMUNE OFFICE

Commune office	Reported manual search time
Commune 1	More than 10 minutes
Commune 2	More than 30 minutes

Commune 3	More than 40 minutes
Commune 4	More than 20 minutes
Commune 5	More than 20 minutes
Average	Approximately 24 minutes

Public burden is an increasing concern, as demonstrated in the citizen survey. Of those surveyed 83.3% reported that they had returned to the commune office more than once for the same document, demonstrating significant inefficiency in the current paper-based system. The survey also indicated that the public is very receptive to digitisation; 76.3% of respondents indicated that they would be willing to use legally valid electronic documents and 77.6% indicated that they would recommend using digital government document services if they were implemented correctly. These two sets of findings show that the problem is severe and a digital solution would be acceptable, and these findings were both instrumental in determining the requirements for the system, particularly in relation to prioritizing fast indexed searching and offline-first capability.

B. Document Retrieval Efficiency

Fig. 1. Document retrieval time comparison.

The system's indexed search yielded search results on the same record type in about 2.5 seconds during formal testing, versus an average of around 24 minutes (approx 1,440 seconds), as per the employee being referenced, from the paper based method. This estimated improvement of about 99.8% (when applying (3)) is the result of performing indexed searches by citizen name, national ID or document number; and replaces having to perform sequential manual searches through folders and filing cabinets.

C. Role-Based Access Control

Table IV
ROLE-BASED ACCESS CONTROL TEST RESULTS

User role	Test cases	Correctly enforced	Compliance
Administrator	10	10	100%
Clerk	10	10	100%
Staff	10	10	100%
Total	30	30	100%

30 tests were used to evaluate access control for each of the three roles. In all cases, the system enforced the appropriate permissions (100% accuracy) as seen in Table

IV. For example, an Administrator could access any function, a Clerk could create, edit or upload a record but not delete a record or manage users, and a Staff member could only view or search for records. No unauthorized access was found.

D. Offline Functionality and Synchronization

Fig. 2. Offline synchronization test results.

40 test cycles were taken to determine offline reliability. In each cycle the client is disconnected from the network while a citizen record or document is uploaded using the offline queue. The connection was then restored and checked to verify that synchronization occurred. As shown in figure 2, out of the 40 cycles 38 were synchronized successfully upon reconnection (95% success rate exceeding the 90% goal), without any data loss or corruption during the test. The two cycles that did not synchronize were timing related. Specifically, Background Synchronization Events occurred before the network connection had stabilized. However, in these cases, the queued data remained safely stored in the IndexedDB and eventually synchronized successfully on a future attempt. As a result, the failures were related to latency rather than data integrity.

E. Performance on Low-Specification Hardware

The test machine, indicated to represent a real-world commune office's average computer (Table II), produced page load times for the system of about 2-3 seconds, which are within acceptable lengths for normal administrative usage, and the lightweight stack can run OK on basic machines. No client installation was necessary except for using a standard web browser.

F User Acceptance

The User Acceptance Testing (UAT) was completed by clerks for each of the five commune offices involved and the clerks were able to test each of the eight core attributes in addition to rating each attribute on ten statements on a Likert scale. As shown in Table V, the overall mean score for these ratings was 4.8 out of 5 (96%) and all attributes received mean scores of 4.4 or higher. The three highest-rated attributes were role-based access control, the

offline upload queue and the backup feature (all scored 5.0); these attributes were borne out of the security and connectivity limitations as identified in the needs assessment, supporting that the design decision was made first and foremost based on painful users' needs. The lowest-rated attribute was the statistics dashboard (score of 4.4) in that while the statistical dashboard was seen as helpful it is not generally viewed as an integral part of daily tasks.

Table V
USER ACCEPTANCE TEST RESULTS BY FEATURE

Feature	Avg (of 5)	Pct.	Interp.
Citizen record management	4.8	96%	Strongly Agree
Document upload	4.8	96%	Strongly Agree
Search and filter	4.6	92%	Strongly Agree
Role-based access control	5.0	100%	Strongly Agree
Offline upload queue	5.0	100%	Strongly Agree
Backup system	5.0	100%	Strongly Agree
Dashboard with statistics	4.4	88%	Strongly Agree
User management	4.8	96%	Strongly Agree
Overall average	4.8	96%	Strongly Agree

V. DISCUSSION

Table VI summarizes the outcomes against the study's objectives. Across all five evaluation strands the proposed system met or exceeded its targets, supporting the study's hypothesis and confirming that an offline-first PWA can deliver reliable document management under commune-office constraints.

Table VI
SUMMARY OF EVALUATION RESULTS

Objective	Metric	Result
Retrieval efficiency	Mean retrieval time	≈24 min → ≈2.5 s (≈99.8%)
Secure access	RBAC test cases passed	30 / 30 (100%)
Offline reliability	Sync success rate	38 / 40 (95%), no data loss
Performance	Page load time	2–3 s on low-spec hardware
User acceptance	UAT average rating	4.8 / 5 (96%)

This research supports past reports showing that EDMS enhances administrative efficiency [6] and that PWAs are best suited for areas that lack reliable Internet connectivity [10][11]. The amount of time reduction seen when retrieving documents using the entire commune's paper records will be much greater than in most of the EDMS literature, which is usually based on a partially digitized data set, whereas the entire commune's paper records were used to create the digital record. The direction of the improvement at the commune level is similar to the study by Gamido et al. on LAN-based EDMSs, which also found a significant amount of time-savings when using an EDMS LAN, which has no dependency on cloud computing [6].

In accordance with Heeks's design-reality gap model [8], this research's main design decision to view connectivity as an enhancer and not as a dependent upon communes rather than expecting to develop or improve the commune infrastructure to meet the assumptions of a cloud system closing the gap by bringing down the system's assumptions to align with the commune's infrastructure: local hosting of one existing computer, using only browsers as clients, and offline queuing. The results also suggest that the same pattern appears to apply to civil record administration from health information systems.

There is a need to take a closer look at both of these sync failures in relation to the operational envelope of the approach. Both sync failures were experienced when the background syncing event was fired during a temporary reconnection window that was unstable; however, both sync failures were resolved upon retry due to there being a durable Queue serving as the system of record until the server acknowledged receipt of the record. With regards to production deployments, these two sync failures suggest two simple hardening techniques: an exponential backoff-and-retry logic around the sync event, and staff being able to easily view a per-item queued status allowing them to check that their pending records were transmitted. These two hardening techniques do not modify the architecture; they merely fine-tune it.

When all of your records are stored in one physical location it changes how you view security rather than just getting rid of any security threat. When there is no longer the threat of being hacked via the internet on a daily basis there is still a new threat in that all the data now resides on one local machine and increases your potential for compromising your physical security, access control, and your ability to restore from backups if those threats materialize. In this case we applied a layered security model that included the use of 100% RBAC enforcement measures used to control access, hashed credentials, encrypted data at rest, audit logs and available timeout period for sessions. The RBAC and backup management systems scored 'perfect' on the UAT evaluation suggest that staff feels secure based on these controls and do not consider them a burden.

Finally, the adoption literature discussed in Section II suggests that EDMS failed mainly due to organizational issues, not technical ones [18]. Hence, two design choices

in study were implemented in response to this: the requirements were directly obtained from the staff who would be using them, not assumed; and, acceptance was measured with those same staff generating an average score of 4.8/5. While these results do not guarantee success for large scale implementation, they do suggest that the system has enough of a fit with existing commune workflows that they will be adopted rather than resisted.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Some limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, the evaluation is not a naturalistic evaluation, but rather an artificial one because it was conducted in a simulated commune environment. Differences in actual hardware, network behaviour and user digital literacy could influence results. Secondly, the amount of time to retrieve the baseline paper records was based on estimates from staff, rather than on objective measures of time taken to perform manual searches. Therefore, the estimate should generally be considered an indication of relative magnitude but not as a precise measure. Thirdly, because user testing had a small number of participants, a broader usability evaluation should be completed across all roles and offices that comprise communes after having completed user acceptance tests with commune clerks. Fourthly, the offline queue has not yet been stress-tested with very large files or extreme network conditions. Lastly, at the present time, the system is functioning solely as a stand-alone solution from one office without inter-commune or national synchronisation (and when backups are required, manual or scheduled local archives are being used), and there is no automated backup to off-site repositories or replication.

Future work will be done sequentially to address these limitations. The next logical step is to undertake a live field deployment, designed as action design research, to achieve design refinement and organizational learning together. This would result in providing the currently missing naturalistic evaluation of the project. Following this, continued work will focus on aligning with provincial and national systems, coordinating the commune level digital civil registration with shared digital public infrastructure and developing a cloud-based disaster recovery plan while also stress testing the offline queue under realistic worst case scenarios.

VII. CONCLUSION

The development of a lightweight document management system developed for low-resource Cambodian Commune offices, using a user-needs assessment of citizen users and commune personnel, was the focus of this research. This system was designed using Laravel, MySQL, Bootstrap 5, and corresponding PWA technologies according to the Design Science Research methodology. It produced: A reduction in document retrieval time from an estimated 24 minutes to approximately 2.5 seconds ($\approx 99.8\%$); A role-based access control (RBAC) system enforced with 100% accuracy across 30 test cases; A 95% success rate with respect to offline synchronization, with no data loss; Page load times

of 2-3 seconds on low-powered machines; and A user acceptance testing (UAT) average score of 4.8 out of 5 (96%) by commune clerks. The overall results of this research support the notion that designing offline-first PWA systems can be replicated as legitimate means by which to support the digitization of Cambodia's public services and particularly civil registration services, in low-connectivity environments, further facilitating the objectives of the Cambodia Digital Government Policy 2022-2035 at the Commune level. Future work includes a live deployment of this system and additional research on broader usability testing with real commune personnel and additional systems synchronization with Provincial and National systems.

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